

Exploring the Stressors in Novice Nursing Students during Clinical Practicum: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Suggested Citation

Malagi, V., Nanjappan, D., & Saha, S. (2024). Exploring the Stressors in Novice Nursing Students during Clinical Practicum: A Cross-Sectional Study. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 557-564.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).49](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).49)

Abstract:

During nursing education, novice students frequently encounter stressors that can disrupt their learning and performance, particularly in the clinical environment. These stressors, which include academic and interpersonal challenges, may affect both mental and physical health. Objective: To identify the stressors experienced by novice nursing students during clinical training. Methods: A survey was conducted with 200 first Nursing students from Smt. Nagarathnamma college of nursing, Bangalore. Participants were selected through convenient sampling, and the Kezkak bilingual questionnaire was used to assess stressors during clinical training.

Results: The most frequently reported stressors were assignments and workload (mean = 1.07, SD = 0.87), emotional environment (mean = 1.1, SD = 0.90), and interpersonal relationships with patients (mean = 1.09, SD = 0.96). The least reported stressors included lack of professional knowledge (mean = 1.11, SD = 0.87) and patient pain and suffering (mean = 1.04, SD = 0.90). Discussion: The findings suggest that workload, emotional challenges, and patient interactions significantly contribute to stress among novice nursing students. These results underscore the importance of providing students with coping mechanisms and support systems to navigate these challenges effectively. Conclusion: Educators should focus on strategies that reduce workload stress and improve emotional resilience, ultimately fostering a better learning environment.

Keywords: *Clinical Practicum, Novice nursing students, Stressors.*

Introduction

Nursing course involves demanding clinical training which requires ability to withstand stressful situations and emergencies. It also requires the ability to be on the feet while on

duty, withstand sleepless nights, cope with emergencies, and handle difficult situation by staying calm and providing support and care to patients and their families. All these facets must be acquired during the training period (Alsaqri, 2017)

Clinical practice is a crucial component of nursing education, offering students the chance to apply theoretical knowledge and develop essential psychomotor and communication skills. The first clinical experience links theory with practice, but it also introduces significant stress for novice students. Throughout their education, nursing students face numerous stressors in the complex clinical environment, which can hinder their learning and performance. These stressors, broadly defined as situations or events that affect health, arise during both academic and clinical training, impacting students' overall well-being and educational outcomes (Rafati, et al., 2017). In addition, they note strained relationships between themselves and clinical preceptors and perceive that the negative attitudes of clinical staff produce stress (Ekstedt, Lindblad, Löfmark, 2019).

Most sources of stress have been categorized as academic, clinical or personal. Each person copes with stress differently. Lazarus (1993), and utilizes deliberate, planned, and psychological efforts to manage stressful demands (Boyd, 2017). Coping mechanisms are commonly termed adaptation strategies or coping skills (Labrague et al., 2017). Noted that students used critical coping strategies to handle stress and suggested that problem solving was the most common coping or adaptation mechanism used by nursing students. Nursing students' coping strategies affect their physical and psychological well-being and the quality of nursing care they offer. Therefore, identifying the coping strategies that students use to manage stressors is important for early intervention (Ni, et al., 2012).

There is little evidence about the causes and effects of stress on Palestinian baccalaureate nursing students during their first clinical placement, as well as their self-initiated stress-coping mechanisms. Also, nursing students train in different settings in Palestinian hospitals, which exposes them to different cultural backgrounds and, as a result, increases stress. Assessing the effect of clinical training stress and developing adequate coping strategies is critical for both nursing students and educators, as it

may encourage the creation of a successful clinical training environment for nursing education. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to examine sources of stress-related during the first clinical training among nursing students at the Arab American University (Toqan, et al., 2023).

A cross-sectional study by Toqan, et al. (2023) was to examine sources of stress-related and coping behaviors during first clinical training among nursing students in the Arab American University. The study was and conducted with a convenience sample of 266 participants of nursing students. Data collection was performed by "Perceived Stress Scale and the Coping Behavior Inventory." The data were analyzed by using the descriptive, that is, frequency and percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The results revealed that the perceived stress mean was 41.2 (SD=19.5). The main stressors were taking care of the patients (M=11.4±0.85) and teachers and nursing staff (M=8.32±5.3). Coping behaviors mean was (M=29.0±15.2). The main coping behavior was problem-solving (M=9.5±5.6). The study confirmed that students perceived moderate levels of stress in their first clinical training, and the most common sources of stress were taking care of the patients and teachers and nursing staff. However, the main coping behavior was problem-solving.

A qualitative study was conducted using semi-structured interviews. Overall, 30 students who were undergoing their first clinical placement in Year 2 at the University of Sharjah between May and June 2022 were recruited. All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim and analyzed for themes. Results During their first clinical training, nursing students are exposed to stress from different sources, including the clinical environment, unfriendly clinical tutors, feelings of disconnection, multiple expectations of clinical staff and patients, and gaps between the curriculum of theory classes and laboratories skills and students' clinical experiences. We extracted three main themes that described students' stress and use of coping strategies during clinical training: (1) managing expectations; (2) theory-practice gap; and (3) learning to cope. Learning to cope, included two

subthemes: positive coping strategies and negative coping strategies. Conclusions This qualitative study sheds light from the students viewpoint about the intricate interplay between managing expectations, theory practice gap and learning to cope. Therefore, it is imperative for nursing faculty, clinical agencies and curriculum planners to ensure maximum learning in the clinical by recognizing the significance of the stressors encountered and help students develop positive coping strategies to manage the clinical stressors encountered. Further research is required look at the perspective of clinical stressors from clinical tutors who supervise students during their first clinical practicum (D'emeh, & Yacoub, 2020)

A descriptive correlational cross-sectional design was used on to a convenience sample of 238 nursing students was recruited. Level and types of stress were measured by Perceived Stress Scale. The data were collected in February 2020. The mean score of perceived stress was 2.58 (SD 0.92). Different sources of stressors perceived by students were identified in current study. The highest type of stressors perceived by students was stress from taking care of patients (mean = 2.81, SD 1.13). In addition, junior students perceived higher level of stress than senior students and female students experienced a higher level of stress than male counterparts. Students who have been supervised by clinical instructors whom their “primary” language is English scored a higher level of stress (Ab Latif, & Mat Nor, 2019).

A descriptive cross-sectional study by Shaban, et al., (2012) was carried out at the Kubang Kerian Nursing College, Kelantan which involved 346 respondents using simple random sampling method. The inclusion criteria were year one, two and three of nursing students who have clinical posting and voluntarily joining the study. Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) and Brief COPE inventory were utilised in the data collection. Higher mean score indicates higher degree of stress. Clinical assignments and workload were the main stressor (mean = 3.19, SD = 1.09). Religion approach was the most coping strategy applied (mean = 3.30, SD = 0.71). Pearson's correlation coefficient test found that six

domains of stressors during clinical practices (taking care of patients; clinical educators/instructors and ward staff; clinical assignments and workload; peers and nursing students from other college; lack of professional knowledge and skills and clinical environment) were statistically significant correlation with coping strategies, where P-value < 0.05. Clinical assignment was the main stressor among nursing students; therefore, successful activities should be promoted to help them in managing clinical assignment and enhancing knowledge in religion.

Impact and Implication in the Indigenous

Identifying stressors among novice nursing students during clinical training has significant implications for improving both their educational experience and patient care quality. Understanding the key stressors, such as workload, emotional challenges, and interpersonal relationships, allows educators to design targeted interventions that alleviate stress. These measures can enhance students' mental well-being, increase their learning efficiency, and reduce burnout. For institutions, addressing these stressors can lead to better student retention, improved academic outcomes, and more competent future healthcare professionals. In clinical practice, less-stressed students are likely to provide safer, more compassionate care, benefiting patients and the healthcare system. The section contains 100 words elaborating the implication of the study findings within the indigenous perspective.

Research Questions

1. What are the primary stressors experienced by novice nursing students during their clinical training?
2. Are there significant differences in stress levels based on socio-demographic factors (e.g., age, gender, educational background)?

Hypotheses

1. Novice nursing students experience significant levels of stress during clinical training

due to factors such as workload, emotional environment, and interpersonal relationships with patients.

2. The stress experienced by novice nursing students negatively affects their clinical performance and learning outcomes.

Methods

Design

A quantitative approach, cross-sectional design was employed in this study. It adopted to understand clinical stressors of novice nursing students. Quantitative content analysis was employed to obtain rich and detailed information from our data. It is a method of systematically coding and categorizing information and comprises a process of comprehending, interpreting, and conceptualizing the key meanings from qualitative data.

Setting and Participants

This study was conducted after the clinical training completion in May 2024, between May and July 24 in the nursing course at the Smt. Nagarathamma College of nursing, Bangalore, RGUHS, in the India. The study population comprised undergraduate and diploma nursing students who were undergoing their first clinical training and were recruited using convenient sampling technique. The inclusion criteria for this study were 1st-year BSc and GNM nursing students of clinical training who could speak English, were willing to participate in this research, and had no previous clinical work experience. The final sample consisted of 200 students.

Research Instrument

The instrumentation package included consent form, demographic sheet and Kezkak bilingual questionnaire. demographic data included 12 items covering the participants' socio-demographic characteristics: age, gender, marital status, residence, percentage secured in second Pre-university course (PUC), educational level, reasons for selecting nursing as a career, parents' educational and occupational status, and

household monthly income. The Kezkak bilingual questionnaire was utilized to identify stressors experienced by novice nursing students during their clinical training. Developed by Xabier Zupiria Gorostidi in 2003, this standardized tool contains 6 domains and 31 items. The items were rated based on the students' last 3 months of clinical experience, using a 4-point Likert scale ranging from "not at all" (0) to "a lot" (3). The reliability of Kezkak bilingual Questionnaire was assessed by Cronbach's Alpha test. The reliability of the tool was $\alpha = 0.95$.

Data Collection

The study was conducted from May 11 to June 18, 2024. Formal written permission was obtained from the Principal of Smt. Nagarathamma College of Nursing, Bangalore. A total of 200 participants, comprising 100 first-year General Nursing and Midwifery students and 100 first-year Basic B.Sc. Nursing students, were selected through non-probability convenient sampling based on the selection criteria. The student researcher introduced herself to each participant, explained the study's purpose, and obtained informed consent while assuring confidentiality. Data was collected from 5 to 10 participants per day. The questionnaire was distributed, and participants were instructed to carefully read and follow the guidelines. Each participant took approximately 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was granted by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) and ethical committees of the selected universities. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose and procedures, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their involvement and their right to decline or withdraw from participation at any time without facing any penalties. Anonymity was ensured by coding the questionnaires, and confidentiality was upheld by limiting access to the collected data.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using IBM SPSS, version 22. Both descriptive and inferential statistical

methods were applied to summarize the sample characteristics and assess the scale items.

Results

Table 1. Characteristics of the Samples

Sl no	Socio-demographic variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage
1	Residence		
	Home	14	7.0
	Relatives	8	4.0
	Hostel	178	89.0
2	Percentage secured in Second Pre-university certificate (PUC)		
	50-70	111	55.5
	71-90	89	44.5
3	Educational level		
	1 st year General nursing and midwifery	100	50.0
	1 st year Basic B.Sc. Nursing	100	50.0
4	Selecting nursing as a career option		
	By your own choice	97	48.5
	Guided by someone	58	29.0
	Forced to opt	16	8.0
	Other	29	14.5
5	Household income (per month in rupees)		
	3500-33500	176	88.0
	33501-63500	21	10.5
	More than 63500	3	1.5

The table 1 indicates that most participants, residing primarily in hostels, come from households with moderate income levels (₹3500-₹33,500 per month). Academically, most of the students secured between 50-70% in their PUC exams. There was an equal representation of students from both General Nursing and

Midwifery, as well as Basic B.Sc. Nursing programs. In terms of career choice, nearly half of the students independently chose nursing, while others were influenced or forced into the profession. This diverse socio-demographic background provides insight into the varying influences and challenges novice nursing students may face during their training.

Table 2. Range, Mean, Standard Deviation and Mean Percentage of Six Domains of Stressors

n=200

SL NO	STRESSORS	RANGE	MEAN	SD	Mean %
1	Lack of professional knowledge and skills	0-24	1.11	0.87	4.62
2	Patient pain and suffering	0-21	1.04	0.90	4.95
3	Nature of clinical practice	0-15	1.15	0.94	7.66
4	Interpersonal relationship with patient	0-12	1.09	0.96	9.08
5	Emotional environment	0-12	1.1	0.90	9.16
6	Assignments and workload	0-9	1.07	0.87	11.88
Total		0-93	6.56	5.44	47.35

The table 2 shows that the primary stressors experienced by participants during their clinical training were assignments and workload (mean

= 1.07, SD = 0.87, mean percentage = 11.88%), the emotional environment (mean = 1.1, SD = 0.90, mean percentage = 9.16%), and

interpersonal relationships with patients (mean = 1.09, SD = 0.96, mean percentage = 9.08%). Conversely, the least significant sources of stress identified were a lack of professional knowledge

and skills (mean = 1.11, SD = 0.87, mean percentage = 4.62%) and the pain and suffering of patients (mean = 1.04, SD = 0.90, mean percentage = 4.95%).

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation of Stressors Experienced by Novice Nursing Students During their Clinical Training

n=200

SL NO	STRESSORS	MEAN	SD
1	Lack of ability to deal with critical situation	1.44	1.040
2	Feel that I can't help the patient	1.34	1.109
3	Feel anxious that I can't get along with my peers	1.30	0.845
4	Fear of making mistakes when caring for a patient	1.25	1.039
5	Unable to deal with terminally-ill patients	1.21	0.767
6	Fear of getting emotionally involved with the patient	1.21	1.019
7	Fear to perform procedures that cause pain to patient	1.20	0.833
8	Don't know how to communicate with the patient	1.20	1.036
9	Unfamiliar with patient medication	1.19	0.847
10	Being with a patient with whom it is difficult to communicate	1.19	0.870
11	Experience pressure while receiving contradictory instructions	1.19	0.792
12	Feel that my responsibility for caring for patient is too much	1.17	0.851
13	Unable to reach the doctor when the situation requires his/her presence	1.16	0.786
14	Fear of being infected with a contaminated needle	1.12	1.025
15	Not feeling integrated into team work	1.13	1.045
16	Don't know how to help patients with physio-psycho-social problems	1.11	1.072
17	Experience pressure from teachers while evaluating clinical performances	1.10	1.004
18	Experience difficulty in changing from the role of student to that of a nurse	1.09	0.825
19	Fear of being infected by the patient	1.08	1.016
20	Afraid that I may cause psychological harm to the patient	1.05	0.849
21	Lack of ability in making judgements	1.04	0.876
22	Don't know how to respond to the patient's expectations	1.03	1.034
23	Unable to provide appropriate responses to health care professionals	1.01	0.776
24	Feel stressed while seeing a patient dying	0.95	0.893
25	Don't know how to conclude conversation with a patient	0.94	0.911
26	Don't know how to respond when the patient disrespects me	0.93	0.914
27	Feel that the requirements of clinical practice exceed my physical and emotional endurance	0.92	0.823
28	Don't know the answers to questions asked by the clinical instructors	0.89	0.841
29	Unfamiliar with professional skills when dealing with the patient	0.88	0.731
30	Feel stressed from the rapid change in patient Condition	0.83	0.758
31	Afraid that I may cause physical harm to the patient	0.81	0.733

The table 3 illustrates that the most prevalent stressors faced by participants during their clinical training were the inability to manage critical situations (mean = 1.44, SD = 1.040), feelings of helplessness in assisting patients (mean = 1.34, SD = 1.109), anxiety about getting along with peers (mean = 1.30, SD = 0.845), and the fear of making mistakes while caring for

patients (mean = 1.25, SD = 1.039). Conversely, the least significant stressors reported were concerns about causing physical harm to patients (mean = 0.81, SD = 0.733) and rapid changes in patient conditions (mean = 0.83, SD = 0.758).

Discussion

The aim of this study was to assess the level and sources of stress among Saudi nursing students during their clinical training. It provided valuable insights into the extent and types of stress experienced by these students. The findings indicate that from assignments and workload of nursing students face a high level of stress, (mean= 1.07, SD= 0.87, mean percentage= 11.88), emotional environment (mean= 1.1, SD= 0.90, mean percentage= 9.16) and interpersonal relationship with patient ((mean=1.09, SD=0.96, mean percentage=9.08). which aligns with the results of other similar studies reporting elevated stress levels in nursing students. (leodoro jabien, 2013). The study result shown that stress from assignments and workload [mean (SD)=2.68 (0.58)] was the most common stressor identified, while emotional symptoms [mean (SD) =1.82 (0.67)] were the most common response to stress. The study concluded that the nursing administrators should diligently evaluate and rectify nursing student's clinical stressors. The similar study by Bothyna and Eman (2012) revealed that many students in their study experienced severe stress, compared to only 28% who had moderate stress. The three sources of stress reported included patient care, peers and daily life events, and hospital staff and instructors.

The present study also revealed that the lowest source of stressors experienced by subjects during their clinical training were from lack of professional knowledge and skills (mean= 1.11, SD= 0.87, mean percentage= 4.62) and patient pain and suffering (mean= 1.04, SD= 0.90, mean percentage= 4.95). Similar study Ahmed, W. A. M., & Mohammed, B. M. A. (2019) findings revealed that students perceived a moderate level of stress (mean 2.10(SD) =0.44) and were in good physio-psycho-social health (mean (SD) =1.40(0.65)). The most common stressor came from "lack of professional knowledge and skills" (mean (SD) =2.34(0.63)). Emotional symptoms commonly occurred in response to clinical stress. Students frequently used transference coping strategy; which they found most effective in dealing with stress in clinical practice.

These findings should prompt nursing educators to closely examine the factors contributing to such significant stress levels and develop strategies to reduce or eliminate these stressors.

Conclusion

The study identified several key stressors experienced by novice nursing students during their clinical training, including assignments, workload, emotional challenges, and interpersonal relationships with patients. These stressors can significantly impact the students' learning, performance, and overall well-being. The findings suggest that addressing these stressors is crucial to improving both the educational experience and the professional development of nursing students.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to all second year nursing students who voluntarily participated in the study.

Abbreviations:

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences,
HAIs: Hospital acquired infections
WHO: World Health Organization

Funding

No funding was received. Not applicable.

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